

Table 1: A list of array variables used in the Fortran program “AL.f” of Warrick (2003)[†].

Name	Size	Definition	Unit
a()	nzmax	$a_i = A_i$	1/(ms)
alpha()	maxlay	$\alpha = h/h_*$	1/m
b()	nzmax	$b_i = B_i$	1/(ms)
bigth()	nzmax	$\Theta = \frac{\theta - \theta_r}{\theta_s - \theta_r}$	unitless
c()	nzmax	$c_i = C_i$	1/(ms)
cond()	nzmax	K	m/s
d()	nzmax	$d_i = D_i$	1/(ms)
depth()	maxlay	Lower depth	m
h()	nzmax	Head at old time	m
hstar()	nzmax	Head at new time	m
ksat()	maxlay	K_s	m/s
m()	maxlay	Fitted parameter	unitless
n()	maxlay	$n = 1/(1 - m)$	unitless
nl()	nzmax	$nl_i = ilayer$	unitless
swc()	nzmax	$swc = \frac{d\theta}{dh}$	1/m
theta()	nzmax	θ	m^3/m^3
timeprint()	np	time output to “out”	s
t_r()	maxlay	θ_r	m^3/m^3
t_s()	maxlay	θ_s	m^3/m^3
z()	nzmax	Center of block	m

[†] A. W. Warrick, 2003. Soil Water Dynamics, Oxford University press, New York. 391 pages.

Table 2: A list of additional array variables used in the extended program “ALS.f”.

Name	Size	Definition	Unit
depf()	maxlay	Depth index for terminating θ profile	<i>m</i>
dept()	ndmax	Daily potential evapotranspiration	<i>mm/d</i>
dlai()	ndmax	Daily leaf area index	<i>m²/m²</i>
drain()	ndmax	Daily rainfall	<i>mm/d</i>
drh()	ndmax	Average daily relative humidity	
dtave()	ndmax	Average daily air temperature	°C
juli()	ndmax	Julian day number	
thef()	maxlay	Profile of θ at the end of the terminating day	
theta()	nzmax	Initial θ profile	
tmprt()	50	time output to “out”	<i>s</i>
tuptak()	nzmax	Accumulated uptake in one depth increment	<i>m</i>
uptake()	nzmax	Average uptake within one increment	<i>1/day, 1/s</i>

Table 3: A list of non-array variables used in the Fortran program “AL.f” of Warrick (2003)

Name	Definition	Unit
b_type	Upper boundary type (1: $h(0, t)$ or $\theta(0, t)$; 2: $J(0, t)$)	
big_bvalue	Top layer effective saturation (S_e) for b_type=1	unitless
bigi	Accumulated infiltration	m
bvalue	Upper boundary: θ or h if b_type=1; flux if b_type=2	depends
c1	K value at the top edge of an upper block	m/s
c2	K value at the top edge of a lower block	m/s
czero	Conductivity at $z = 0$ for b_type=1	m/s
diff_99	Soil water diffusivity at $\Theta = 0.99$	m^2/s
dtmax	Maximum dt ($300s = 5min$)	s
dtmin	Minimum dt ($1s$)	s
dtpress	Multiple for increasing dt	unitless
dz	dz ($= 0.025m$)	m
dz2	dz^2	m^2
f1	Flux through top edge of a block with node centered	m/s
f2	Flux through bottom edge of a block with node centered	m/s
flux	Upper boundary flux for b_type=2	m/s
fourier	Fourier grid number, $r = D \delta t / dz^2$	
hinit	Initial pressure head (matric potential)	m
hstar	Pressure head for new time (output of Thomas)	m
hzero	Upper boundary pressure head for b_type=1	m
ilayer	Index of soil layer (1, 2, ..., 10)	
ipr	Index for printing?	m
it	Index for time iteration (1, 2, ...,)	
iz	Index for depth iteration (1, 2, ..., nz)	
ninfp	Frequency for writing to output file	
nlayer	Number of soil layers with input hydraulic parameters	
np	A number controlling output printing	
nz	Number of space divisions for finite difference scheme	
smalli	Relative infiltration (i/K_s)	unitless
t	Time	s
wadd	Total amount of water added to the soil profile	m
water	Scratch variable for computing added water	m
wbelow	Amount of water due to deep drainage	m
wstart	Total amount of water in profile prior to time iteration	m

Table 4: A list of additional non-array variables used in the extended program “ALS.f”

Name	Definition	Unit
ard	Average relative discrepancy	
beta	Root distribution shape factor	
big_bv	Scratch variable for Θ , or relative saturation	
c_aeva	Actual cumulative evaporation	<i>m</i>
c_atra	Actual cumulative evaporation	<i>m</i>
ck	Average canopy transmission coefficient (= 0.4)	
diff99	Same as diff_99 as in AL (see Table ??)	
dl	Daily leaf area index	m^2/m^2
dnorm	Normalized day of growth in Equation ??	
dt	Time step	<i>s</i>
eat	Actual soil evaporation	<i>m/s</i>
ep	Potential soil evaporation	<i>m/s</i>
etpd	Daily potential evapotranspiration	<i>mm/d</i>
i	Index variable for various do loops	
identi	Character variable for identification	
initio	Flag for initial θ type	
jmatur	Julian day number for growth maturity	
jthaw	Julian day number for growth initiation	
julid	Julian day number	
maxlay	Number of soil layers with unique physical parameters	
nd	Number of days passed since the start of simulation	
ndmax	Maximum number of days needed to run the model	
nn	Number of depths with final soil water measurement	
nobs	Number of data points for the interpolated initial θ profile	
nzmax	Maximum number of vertical increment	
psi	Matric potential at the soil-air interface	<i>m</i>
rain	Rainfall rate	<i>mm/d</i> , or <i>m/s</i>
rh	Average daily relative humidity (as a fraction)	
tave	Average daily air temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
thefm	Averaged or measured terminating soil water content	m^3/m^3
tpd	Daily potential transpiration	<i>mm/d</i>
updt dz	Total uptake for chosen <i>dt</i> and <i>dz</i>	<i>m</i>
zrmax	Maximum rooting depth	<i>m</i>
zrt	Variable rooting depth	<i>m</i>